

Constraints on $SU(2)_L$ -preserving NSI from τ decays

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Abstract

Neutrino non-standard interactions (NSI) have been studied in a variety of contexts and suggested as a possible mechanism for resolving certain unexpected results in oscillation experiments. NSI may be generated in various ways and take a variety of forms. We focus on flavor-changing neutral current NSIs involving tau neutrinos. In simple scenarios in which these are generated by dimension-six effective operators, it is often the case that flavor-violating interactions of charged leptons are also generated; the strengths of these interactions are then related by $SU(2)_L$ symmetry. We investigate for this subset of NSI the restrictions which can be obtained by utilizing the stringent experimental limits on charged lepton flavor-violating tau decays, finding that the quark contributions to these operators are often constrained to be on the order of 10^{-3} .

1 Introduction

The neutrino sector has the potential to be a valuable portal to physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM). Flavor oscillations of the neutrinos and, by implication of these, nonzero neutrino masses are already BSM physics, and as experimentalists continue to work on pinning down with greater precision the basic properties of neutrinos, further new physics may appear. One direction of interest in this regard is neutrino non-standard interactions (NSI), which have been investigated (see [1–4], among others) as a possible resolution to several unexpected experimental results.

Meanwhile, another search for BSM physics is underway in the charged lepton sector. The conservation of lepton flavor is an accidental symmetry of the Standard Model (SM), and violations of it are expected to be highly suppressed and effectively unobservable at present. However, various new-physics scenarios allow for violations potentially many orders of magnitude greater than the SM predicts, thus making charged lepton flavor violation (CLFV) an attractive experimental target. Thus far, no CLFV has been observed, and highly restrictive constraints have been obtained.

The $SU(2)_L$ symmetry of the SM, broken at low energies but expected to be preserved at the high energies where new BSM interactions may be generated, relates the neutrinos with their charged lepton counterparts. New interactions at high energies in the unbroken phase would lead to new effective interactions at low energies, with the symmetry potentially inducing a relationship between the interaction strengths for neutrinos and those for charged leptons (as seen, e.g., in [5] and [6]). Although there are several ways to evade these relationships (some examples of which we briefly mention in Sec. 3 below), it is still worth considering what the strict experimental bounds on CLFV may imply about the strength of NSI with a related origin. This may also be of interest to those investigating the phenomenology of particular BSM models in which NSI and CLFV would be generated together.

2 Methods

There are a number of possibilities for new interactions involving neutrinos. Generalized neutrino interactions (GNI) allow for all possible Dirac structures and for the potential existence of right-handed neutrinos [7]. The subset of GNI comprising vector interactions of the left-handed neutrinos make up the NSI, which can further be subdivided into charged current NSI and neutral current NSI. The latter are particularly relevant as potential new matter effects, and take the form

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NSI(NC)}} = -2\sqrt{2}G_F \sum_{f,X,\alpha,\beta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{fX} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma^\mu P_L \nu_\beta) (\bar{f} \gamma_\mu P_X f), \quad (1)$$

where G_F is the Fermi constant, f is a charged fermion, $P_X = (1 \mp \gamma_5)/2$ for $X \in \{L, R\}$, and α and β are flavor indices running over $\{e, \mu, \tau\}$. One can rearrange the chiral contributions into vector (V) and axial-vector (A) contributions as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NSI(NC)}} = -\sqrt{2}G_F \sum_{f,\alpha,\beta} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma^\mu P_L \nu_\beta) \left(\bar{f} \left[\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{fV} \gamma_\mu + \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{fA} \gamma_\mu \gamma_5 \right] f \right). \quad (2)$$

In ordinary media, the NSI contributions to the matter effect come from $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{fV}$ [8]. However, in the case of only a single new interaction with a chiral fermion, both V and A contributions would be generated with the same magnitude. Due to the large number of potential new interactions, we will be presenting bounds assuming only one new interaction at a time; in this framework, a bound on the A contribution becomes equivalent to a bound on the V contribution. One should keep in mind, though, that interference between multiple new interactions could lead to suppression of CLFV and enhancement of NSI. Additionally, while strange-quark contributions to the NSI would not be expected to be relevant in normal matter, we include them here for completeness when they arise (and also in case they are of interest to those studying more exotic scenarios).

Following the methods of Bergmann et al. [5], we consider the simple scenario in which a single new interaction above the electroweak breaking scale is described at low energies by an effective four-fermion operator of mass dimension six; this operator would then give rise to the NSI if it involves (either directly or by Fierz rearrangement) a current of the form given in Eq. 1. However, due to the $SU(2)_L$ symmetry, typically a related interaction will also be generated, with the neutrinos replaced by their charged-lepton counterparts (either with the same background fermions or with their $SU(2)_L$ partners). These interactions would then take the form

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CLFV}} = -2\sqrt{2}G_F \sum_{f,X,\alpha,\beta} C_{\alpha\beta}^{fX} (\bar{l}_\alpha \gamma^\mu P_L l_\beta) (\bar{f} \gamma_\mu P_X f). \quad (3)$$

The strength of the CLFV interactions could be the same as the NSI, or they could vary due to $SU(2)_L$ -breaking effects (as discussed further in Sec. 3), but in general they should agree to within less than an order of magnitude.

Under all these assumptions, one can use the stringent constraints on CLFV τ decays coming from the BaBar [9–11] and Belle [12–14] experiments (at SLAC and KEK, respectively, and averaged by HFLAV [15]) to derive bounds on flavor-violating neutral current NSI involving tau neutrinos. We aim to take advantage of these new experimental results to improve on the bounds first obtained by Bergman et al. [5] using the best available results at the time, namely, those of the CLEO experiment at CESR [16,17]. As the limits on the CLFV branching ratios have improved by two orders of magnitude, the limits on the coefficients of the effective operators should improve by one order of magnitude. We also hope to improve the analysis by using the the decay $\tau \rightarrow l\pi^+\pi^-$ (with $l \in \{e, \mu\}$ throughout) to constrain the isovector component of the vector NSI; for this, we employ the parametrization of [18], together with the phase-smoothing method described in [19], to describe the pion vector form factor. Finally, while the original analysis of Bergmann et al. [5] proposed the use of the decay $\tau \rightarrow l\omega$ to

constrain the isoscalar component of the vector NSI, this was not possible at the time due to the lack of an experimental upper bound on the process; however, such bounds now exist [11,14], and therefore we are able to include this decay in our analysis.

3 Limitations

As mentioned above, use of CLFV to constrain NSI relies on several assumptions, and thus the bounds may not apply in various scenarios. One such possibility is if the NSI is instead due to dimension-eight operators involving the Higgs doublet; in this case, after electroweak symmetry breaking one can obtain NSI of a more substantial magnitude while still respecting the current experimental limits on CLFV [20,21]. Additionally, the total NSI matter effect $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}$ is a weighted sum over the contributions of electrons and up and down quarks; here, we are only constraining the light-quark contributions. Electron contributions have been considered elsewhere (see, e.g., [6] and [7]) and shown to be significantly constrained by CLFV searches as well, but could still enhance the net NSI strength beyond the bounds obtained here.

Our bounds assume only one new interaction at a time, but properly they apply only to linear combinations of the various quark contributions, which are not in general the same as the weighted sum implicit in the definition of the NSI parameters $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}$. There is also the issue that the same type of NSI could arise as the result of multiple new interactions (generated by operators corresponding to different mediators), further complicating any attempt to disentangle the possible contributions of the individual quark flavors.

It is also important to recall that only in the case of the $SU(2)_L$ singlets do the bounds apply directly (i.e., the effective NSI coupling $\epsilon_{l\tau}^q$ has magnitude equal to that of the CLFV coupling $C_{l\tau}^q$). The effective coupling, however, is inversely proportional to the mediator mass squared, and thus in the case of $SU(2)_L$ doublet or triplet mediators a bound on $C_{l\tau}^q$ is really a bound on $\epsilon_{l\tau}^q$ multiplied by the ratio of the squares of the mediator masses. In the original work of Bergmann et al. [5], however, lepton universality constraints were used to demonstrate that this effect cannot weaken the bounds by more than a factor of 7.

4 Results

As mentioned above, the bounds obtained on the coefficients of operators giving rise to CLFV may give direct or indirect constraints on the related NSI, depending on the mediator of the new interaction. We therefore report bounds on the magnitude $|C_{l\tau}^q|$ of the CLFV coefficients, assuming only one nonzero $C_{l\tau}^q$ at a time, with the understanding that the applicability of these bounds to constrain NSI depends on the origin of the new physics. (For details, see [5]; we will provide our own commentary in the forthcoming work [22].) To reduce uncertainty, we normalize the flavor-violating process by the flavor-conserving one using the relation

$$\frac{\text{BR}(\text{FV})}{\text{BR}(\text{FC})} = \frac{\Gamma(\text{FV})}{\Gamma(\text{FC})}, \quad (4)$$

except for the decays $\tau \rightarrow l\omega$, which we describe with a Breit-Wigner. The Breit-Wigner description is appropriate for the ω due to its narrow width, but we would have to normalize with the decay involving ρ^- , which is a broad resonance requiring the use of a form factor; this would introduce additional uncertainty and result in a significantly different functional form, preventing the expected cancellations which motivate the normalization strategy in the other cases. We do, however, use the form factor for the decay involving $\pi^+\pi^-$ (as mentioned above), since the decay used for normalization then involves $\pi^-\pi^0$ which can be approximated, up to a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ [23], as having the same form factor.

We present our *preliminary* results in Tables 1 and 2. (Final results will be published in [22]). We find that the decays $\tau \rightarrow lP^0$, where P^0 is a pseudoscalar meson, provide constraints on the

axial component of the NSI on the order of 10^{-3} . We also find that the decays $\tau \rightarrow l\pi^+\pi^-$ and $\tau \rightarrow l\omega$, which probe the vector component, provide constraints on the order of 10^{-4} .

Process	Dirac Structure	Isospin	$ C_{\mu\tau}^{uX} $ Constraint	$ C_{\mu\tau}^{dX} $ Constraint	$ C_{\mu\tau}^{sX} $ Constraint
$\tau \rightarrow \mu\pi^0$	Axial	1	$< 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$	N/A
$\tau \rightarrow \mu\eta$	Axial	0	$< 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 9.6 \times 10^{-4}$
$\tau \rightarrow \mu\eta'$	Axial	0	$< 2.6 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 2.6 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$
$\tau \rightarrow \mu\pi^+\pi^-$	Vector	1	$< 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	$< 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	N/A
$\tau \rightarrow \mu\omega$	Vector	0	$< 5.8 \times 10^{-4}$	$< 5.8 \times 10^{-4}$	N/A

Table 1: Preliminary constraints on $|C_{\mu\tau}^{qX}|$ (with $X \in \{L, R\}$) obtained from experimental limits on the flavor-violating decays $\tau \rightarrow \mu + \text{hadrons}$, assuming one nonzero coefficient at a time.

Process	Dirac Structure	Isospin	$ C_{e\tau}^{uX} $ Constraint	$ C_{e\tau}^{dX} $ Constraint	$ C_{e\tau}^{sX} $ Constraint
$\tau \rightarrow e\pi^0$	Axial	1	$< 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$	N/A
$\tau \rightarrow e\eta$	Axial	0	$< 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
$\tau \rightarrow e\eta'$	Axial	0	$< 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$	$< 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$
$\tau \rightarrow e\pi^+\pi^-$	Vector	1	$< 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	$< 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$	N/A
$\tau \rightarrow e\omega$	Vector	0	$< 4.7 \times 10^{-4}$	$< 4.7 \times 10^{-4}$	N/A

Table 2: Preliminary constraints on $|C_{e\tau}^{qX}|$ (with $X \in \{L, R\}$) obtained from experimental limits on the flavor-violating decays $\tau \rightarrow e + \text{hadrons}$, assuming one nonzero coefficient at a time.

5 Conclusion

Flavor-violating τ decays continue to provide strong indirect constraints on the quark contribution to NSI, subject to assumptions of an $SU(2)_L$ connection between the operators responsible for NSI and those which would generate CLFV. We find bounds on the order of $10^{-3} - 10^{-4}$ in a variety of cases, including from the decay $\tau \rightarrow l\omega$, which was proposed by Bergmann et al. [5] but experimentally bounded only recently [11, 14]. Although a variety of mechanisms exist by which these bounds could be evaded, and therefore we cannot rule out sizable flavor-violating NSI in general, these results suggest that more modest values are to be expected in the simplest new-physics scenarios.

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